

NACRE-INSPIRED, STRONG AND DUCTILE CNT/AL COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY FLAKE POWDER METALLURGY

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Keywords: *Aluminum; Carbon nanotubes; Biomimetic; Ductility; Flake powder metallurgy*

Abstract

In order to combine high tensile strength and ductile behavior, a nacre-inspired CNT/Al nanolaminated composite stacked alternatively with parallel aligned CNTs and Al lamellae was fabricated by a bottom-up flake powder metallurgy route, using Al nanoflakes and carboxyl functionalized carbon nanotube (CNT) as starting materials. Compared to conventional homogeneous nanocomposites composed of the same constituents, the final bulk product with nacre-like architecture exhibits a simultaneous enhancement in tensile strength and uniform elongation.

1 Introduction

Incorporating CNTs into light metals and alloys, such as Al, was supposed to make a new class of engineering nanocomposites with both high strength and good ductility, which is suitable for the automotive or aerospace industries. However, for lack of effective fabrications method and proper architecture design, the as-prepared CNT/Al nanocomposites usually failed to fully realize strengthening efficiency of CNTs and achieve satisfying ductility, which is an obvious drawback to their practical applications [1-2]. Herein, a new strategy to tailor the structure of CNT/Al nanocomposites and thus endowing such materials with both high strength and good ductility is in great demand.

Nacre has gained tremendous interest as a model system for developing composites with good combination of strength and toughness. In nacre, the laminated assembly of alternating protein collagen layers (10–50 nm thick) and aragonite tablets (200–900 nm thick) contributes to remarkable mechanical properties far beyond that which can be achieved by man-made composites [3-4]. Inspired by nacre, there are increasing efforts to artificially create or

biomimick nacre's nanolaminated structures in metal-matrix composites (MMCs).

2 Fabrication of nacre-like CNT/Al composites

In this report, a bottom-up strategy based on the recently developed flake powder metallurgy (Flake PM) route [5] was used to fabricate CNT/Al composites with nacre-like nanolaminated structure, in which layers of Al (~400nm) and CNTs (~50nm) were alternatively stacked. As illustrated in Fig.1, the Flake PM process includes changing the spherical Al powders (10 μm in diameter) into nanoflakes (diameter of 45μm and thickness of 300-500nm), adsorbing CNTs onto Al nanoflakes, forcing nanoflakes stack orderly into nanolaminates with 2-D distribution of CNTs by compacting, finally extrusion to force CNTs to align between Al nanolaminates and form a dense nanocomposite.

3 Results and discussion

After extrusion, the dense nanocomposites fabricated by Flake PM show that all the Al platelets with aligned CNTs are organized with their faces parallel to extrusion direction (Fig.2a). The extruded multilayer structure with alternating Al (~400nm) and CNT (~50nm) layers can be clearly observed in Fig.2b. While, obviously seen in Fig.2c and d, CNTs exhibit disorientation and form a 3-D random distribution in the conventional PM nanocomposites.

The resulting tensile properties of 1 vol% CNT/Al nanocomposites fabricated by conventional PM and Flake PM are shown in Fig.3a. The Flake PM CNT/Al nanocomposite shows a plasticity of 12% at tensile strength of 375 MPa, while the conventional PM nanocomposite exhibits only a plasticity of 6% at tensile strength of 330 MPa. Therefore, CNT/Al nanocomposites with the high level ordering nanolaminates exhibited both greatly

improved tensile strength and plasticity compared with nanocomposites composed of the same constituents but randomly distributed CNTs.

The increased strength was mainly attributed to the nanolaminate structure, which enhanced the 2-D alignment of CNTs through geometric confinement and thus enabled the improved longitudinal properties of CNTs in matrix. The strengthening efficiency of CNTs (R) can be expressed as:

$$R = (\sigma_c - \sigma_m) / V_f \sigma_m \quad (1)$$

Where σ_c and σ_m are the tensile strength of nanocomposites and matrix respectively, and V_f is volume fraction of CNTs. In the CNT/Al nanocomposite by Flake PM, the enhanced alignment of CNTs enables the R of 27, much higher than the R (7.5) of conventional PM nanocomposites with 3-D randomly distributed CNTs.

A better appreciation of the unique mechanical properties of the CNT/Al nanolaminated composites can be gained by comparing with those fabricated by other processes. As shown in Fig.3b, most CNT/Al nanocomposites with randomly distributed CNTs have a strength-ductility trade-off; that is, high strength accompanied with low ductility (points inside the purple region). However, the Flake PM nanocomposites (a red point outside the purple region) exhibit both high strength and good ductility, indicating the possibility of retaining good ductility in CNT/Al nanolaminated composites. Thus, the Flake PM and relevant nanolaminate design were proved to be a practical and effective solution for strong CNT/Al nanocomposites with remarkable ductility.

Fig.1 Flake PM process for fabricating nacre-like CNT/Al composite.

Fig.2 Microstructure of CNT/Al nanocomposites fabricated by Flake PM (a,b), and conventional PM (c,d).

Fig.3 Tensile properties of CNT/Al nanocomposites (a) loading with 1 vol.% CNTs and fabricated by conventional PM and Flake PM, inset shows the relevant strengthening efficiencies of CNTs; (b) fabricated by various methods, the data was drawn based on recent reviews (Ref. [1] and [2])

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